

P-Value: a true test of significance in agricultural research

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P-values are widely used in both the social and natural sciences to quantify the statistical significance of observed results. The significance level, also denoted as alpha or α , is the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is true. The p-value is based on two hypotheses. One of these is the null hypothesis, in which it is normally assumed that there is no difference or no effect of a treatment or an exposure. The second is alternative hypothesis which is often an assumption that the null hypothesis is untrue. Then a set of mathematical-statistical methods are applied to estimate the probability of what we are observing, given that the null hypothesis is actually correct. The p stands for probability and measures how likely it is that any observed difference between groups is due to chance (Dahiru, 2008). For example, a significance level of .05 indicates a 5% risk of concluding that a difference exists when there is no actual difference. For ease of comparison, researchers often feature the p-value in the hypothesis test and allow the reader to interpret the statistical significance themselves. This is called a p-value approach to hypothesis testing. The significance level determines how far out from the null hypothesis value we will draw that line on the graph. A significance level of .05, we need to shade the 5% of the distribution that is furthest away from the null hypothesis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Two-tailed critical region for a significance level of 0.05 (Source: Minitab Blog, 2019)

In Figure 1 from null hypothesis value, the two shaded areas are equidistant and each area consist of a probability of .025, for a total of .05. In statistics, these shaded areas known as

the *critical region* for a two-tailed test. If the population mean is 260, we had expect to obtain a sample mean which falls in the critical region 5% of the time. The critical region defines how far away our sample statistic must be from the null hypothesis value before we can say it is unusual enough to reject the null hypothesis.

In Figure 2, our sample mean (330.6) falls within the critical region, this indicates it is statistically significant at the .05 level. We can also see if it is statistically significant using the other common significance level of .01.

Figure 2. Two-tailed critical region for a significance level of 0.01 (Source: Minitab Blog, 2019)

The two shaded areas each have a probability of .005, which adds up to a total probability of .01. This time our sample mean does not fall within the critical region and we fail to reject the null hypothesis. This comparison shows why you need to choose your significance level before you begin your study. It protects you from choosing a significance level because it conveniently gives you significant result.

The levels of significance may be 5%, 1% and 0.1%, empirically corresponding to a “confidence level” of 95%, 99% and 99.9%, respectively. In social science, $p < .1$ considers at 10% level of significant due to more heterogeneity of data set where as in medical science it will be $p = .01$ (1% level or less). In the field experiments, p -value is generally calculated at 5% level of significance. The p -values that are $\leq .05$ are considered to be significant, whereas p -values that are $> .05$ are not significant (Fay and Gerow, 2019). If the p -value is greater than .05, then the result is not statistically significant. A p -value less than .05 (typically $\leq .05$) is statistically significant. We reject the null hypothesis, and accept the alternative hypothesis. A p -value higher than .05 ($> .05$) is not statistically significant. We fail to reject the null hypothesis and cannot accept the alternative hypothesis. The .05 threshold is completely

arbitrary and p values as such are inappropriate to guide clinical or scientific decision making. Significance is thereby defined very narrowly and must not be confused with clinical relevance or even meaning of findings (Dick and Tevæarai, 2015).

In every experiment, there is an effect or difference between groups that the researchers are testing. Unfortunately for the researchers, there is always the possibility that there is no effect, that is, that there is no difference between the groups. This lack of a difference is called the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis is true: there is no difference between the experimental groups at the population level. Despite the null being true, it's entirely possible that there will be an effect in the sample data due to random sampling error. Many researchers would like to report positive findings based on previously reported researches as "non-significant results should not take up" journal space (Berking et al., 1989; Stern and Smith, 2001). In general, journals publish articles that report one or more statistically significant effects. It puts tremendous pressure on researchers to produce significant results. At times, researchers may turn to malpractice called p -hacking to get the results they desire. A study that is found to be statistically significant may not necessarily be practically significant (Hojat and Xu, 2004). There is difference between statistical significance and practical significance. Normally, the objective of a medical or clinical research study is to draw conclusions regarding the effect of a treatment or exposure and the magnitude of this effect. Thus, the p -value is not a measure of this probability and provides little information on the medical effect. A p value $< .05$ may be significant statistically, but never proves clinical significance.

LSD (Least Significant Difference) is the value at a particular level of statistical probability ($P \leq 0.01$ - means with 99% accuracy and $P \leq 0.05$ - means with 95% accuracy) when exceeded by the difference between two varietal means for a particular characteristic, then the two varieties are said to be distinct for that characteristic at that or lesser levels of probability. Generally LSD is calculated at $p \leq .01$ and $p \leq .05$. The formula for the least significant difference is:

$$LSD_{A,B} = t_{0.05/2, DFW} \sqrt{MSW(1/n_A + 1/n_B)}$$

Where: t = critical value from the t -distribution table, MSW = mean square within, obtained from the results of your ANOVA test. n = number of scores used to calculate the means.

Least significant difference is used to compare means of different treatments that have an equal number of replications. The difference between two mean values is compared to the LSD value. If the difference is greater than the LSD value, then the means are significantly different. Least Significant Difference means that the yields must be greater than the LSD value between any two hybrids, varieties or treatments to be considered significant, to make sure the differences are real and not because of chance or due to soil variability. LSD value measures variability in the test which may be caused by soil types, population density variations, micro-environment or experimental errors. Uniform tests have smaller LSD values and are more reliable.

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